

The control system of an immersive wheelchair simulator

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Abstract—This paper presents the control architecture of a novel wheelchair simulator to support the training phase in a controlled and safe environment. It is composed by a virtual reality system and a parallel mechatronic platform, in order to provide proper vestibular and haptic feedbacks to the patient. The system allows to simulate both electronic and manual wheelchair, by the use of a couple of sensorized and motorized haptic wheels.

Index Terms—Wheelchair Simulator, Control Architecture, Motion Cueing Algorithm, Washout Filter

I. INTRODUCTION

Operating a wheelchair may not be an easy task since it requires a good combination of different skills, such as vision, strength, endurance, orientation and perception of the surrounding space [1], [2]. For this reason, people forced on a wheelchair following an accident, may experience difficulties in driving, that may lead to the practice of wrong behaviors, unsafe for oneself and others, that in long/medium term could also bring to isolation and a low quality of life [2]–[4].

In order to make easier the return to work and social life for people after accident, it is a good practice to assist the users during a period of intense training on wheelchair, experiencing the driving in different safe and controlled scenarios. One possible training tool for wheelchair users is the simulator [2] that allows to train in a repeatable, controlled and safe environment. Within this context, an immersive wheelchair simulator for training patients is currently being developed and presented here. Several studies have shown that the effectiveness of training through virtual reality is positively correlated to the sense of presence perceived by the user during the simulation; particular attention is therefore paid to this aspect and to the factors that contribute to increasing the perception of "feeling immersed" within a virtual environment [5]. In these terms, the capability of emulating the physical behaviour of the wheelchair, by generating proper vestibular and haptic feedbacks to the patient is crucial.

A Parallel Kinematic (PKM) platform controlled by a proper Motion Cueing Algorithm (MCA) is being realized to move the patient in order to reproduce the motions and the physical

interaction with the physical world. MCAs have been considered widely for vehicles including car simulator [6] [7] [8], motorbike simulator [9] and airplane simulator [10], but, in the context of wheelchair simulator, to the best of authors' knowledge, MCAs are still poorly investigated, despite the fact some typical movements of wheelchairs have a different characteristic or even greater motion range and motion rate compared to other vehicles.

This work, after having introduced the main components of the mechatronic platform, focuses on the control system and architecture of the simulator.

II. THE MECHATRONIC PLATFORM

The wheelchair simulator (Fig.1) is composed by two main part: a mechatronic platform and a virtual reality system (VR) equipped with a physics engine. The mechatronic platform consists of a seat, adaptable to different patient sizes, moved in space by a parallel Gough-Stewart platform (MOOG MB-E-6DOF/1000 Kg). The user can interact with the VR and move

Fig. 1. The mechatronic platform

within it in two ways: either through a joystick, as for an electronic wheelchair, or through a pair of haptic wheels sensorized and actuated by a torque motor, in order to emulate the behaviour of a manual wheelchair. The commands provided by the user, through the joystick or the haptic wheels, are used as reference to navigate within the virtual environment. The visual feedback is provided to the user through a head-mounted display (HTC VIVE) while the motion of the parallel platform is controlled consistently with the movement of the virtual wheelchair represented by the VR.

III. THE CONTROL SYSTEM

The simulator control architecture considered is sketched in Fig.2. The control architecture is divided in high(HL) and low level(LL). The HL controller is responsible for pose setpoints calculation; this level exploit a CWF algorithm to render a realistically motion considering the PKM dof physical limits. The MCA currently being developed is based on CWF with properly tuned control parameters. In details, the CWF is characterized by three different input channels: translational, rotational and coordination channels (Fig. 3). While the first two channels are converted in translational acceleration and rotation angle inputs movement. The third channel (i.e., coordination channels) is converted in rotation of PKM which, thanks to gravity, is perceived by the user as a low-frequency acceleration. Finally, due to the physical limitation of the platform, the platform must slowly return to the neutral position (return-to-zero block) in order to have a good starting point for the next movement. To simulate a manual wheelchair, the simulator is also equipped with two haptic wheels. These wheels are driven by direct motors and the torque is measured from the winding current. The torque measurements are sent to the physical engine in the HL that respond with kinematic commands for wheels controller. This LL control communicates with drivers through an EtherCAT bus. The LL control is responsible for the motion control of the mechatronic platform and wheels, and ensures that the system correctly reproduces the trajectory defined by the HL. The controller is implemented in ROS framework following the *ros_control* guide lines.

Fig. 2. Architecture of the mechatronic platform.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORKS

The simulator under development will be used to simulate both outdoor and indoor environments. The former typically features elements of possible disturbance such as cars and pedestrians, the latter characterized by relatively narrow spaces and limited maneuvering spaces.

A clear direction for future research realizes the use of optimal and adaptive washout filters for the high-level controller. Moreover, the study of applying artificial intelligent techniques to adapt the control system to the driving style or level of impairment of patients would be another interesting topic for our research.

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Fig. 3. The MCA algorithm.